

AN APPROACH GENERATING AUGMENTED DATA FOR MACHINE LEARNING DATA PROCESSING

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Many datasets in industrial applications, especially during the initial phase of the digital transformation process, are composed by few records. In order to use machine learning algorithms, it is important to improve the self-learning models increasing the record number of the dataset. In this direction, it is possible to increase the record number of the training dataset by means of augmented data. An approach to consider is the data randomization around the average value of the few available data (basic dataset). The randomization can be performed between thresholds of about $\pm x\%$, where x can be optimized in function of the oscillation behavior of the original dataset.

Figure: Example of Augmented Data generated from a basic dataset.